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Avian influenza A viruses in human: An emerging infectious disease

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Pandemic of Influenza

An influenza pandemic is a global outbreak of disease that occurs when a new influenza A virus appears or “emerges” in the human population, causes serious illness, and then spreads easily from person to person worldwide. Pandemics are different from seasonal outbreaks or “epidemics” of influenza. Seasonal outbreaks are caused by subtypes of influenza viruses that are already in existence among people, whereas pandemic outbreaks are caused by new subtypes or by subtypes that have never circulated among people or that have not circulated among people for a long time. Past influenza pandemics have led to high levels of illness, death, social disruption, and economic loss. Influenza outbreaks are recorded virtually every year, although their extent and severity vary widely. Localized outbreaks take place at variable intervals, usually every 1 to 3 years. Except for the past two decades, global epidemics or pandemics have occurred approximately every 10 to 15 years since the 1918-1919 pandemic.

The most extensive and severe outbreaks are caused by influenza A viruses. In part, this predominance is a result of **the remarkable propensity of the H and N antigens of influenza A virus to undergo periodic antigenic variation.**

Major antigenic variations are referred to as antigenic shifts, which may be associated with pandemics and are restricted to influenza A viruses. Minor variations are called antigenic drifts. These antigenic changes may involve the hemagglutinin alone or both the hemagglutinin and the neuraminidase. In human infections, three major antigenic subtypes of hemagglutinins (H1, H2, and H3) and two of neuraminidases (N1 and N2) have been recognized. An example of an antigenic shift involving both the hemagglutinin and the neuraminidase is that of 1957, when the predominant influenza A virus subtype shifted from **H1N1** to **H2N2**; this shift resulted in a severe pandemic, with an estimated 70,000 excess deaths (i.e., deaths in excess of the number expected without an influenza epidemic) in the United States alone. In 1968, an antigenic shift involving only the hemagglutinin occurred (H2N2 to H3N2); the subsequent pandemic was less severe than that of 1957. In 1977, an H1N1 virus emerged and caused a pandemic that primarily affected younger individuals (i.e., those born after 1957).

H1N1 viruses circulated from 1918 to 1956. During most outbreaks of influenza A, a single subtype has circulated at a time. However, since

1977, H1N1 and H3N2 viruses have circulated simultaneously, resulting in outbreaks of varying severity. In some outbreaks, influenza B viruses have also circulated simultaneously with influenza A viruses.

The origin of pandemic strains is unknown. Given the marked differences between the primary structures of the hemagglutinins of different subtypes of influenza A viruses (H1, H2, and H3), it seems unlikely that antigenic shifts result from spontaneous mutations in the hemagglutinin gene. Because the segmented genome of influenza viruses may result in high rates of reassortment, it has been suggested that pandemic strains may emerge by reassortment of genes between human and animal viruses. There was concern that such reassortment might have occurred in 1997 in Hong Kong, where cases of infection caused by influenza virus A/H5N1 were detected in humans during an extensive outbreak of avian influenza A/H5N1 in poultry. However, only a few cases of A/H5N1 influenza in humans were documented, and the infection did not spread into the community. Influenza B viruses do not have an animal reservoir and do not undergo antigenic shifts [1, 2, 3, 4].

Transmission of Influenza A Viruses between Animals and People Influenza A viruses are found in many different animals, including ducks, chickens, pigs, whales, horses, and seals. However, certain subtypes of influenza A virus are specific to certain species, except for **birds which are hosts to all subtypes of influenza A**. Subtypes that have caused widespread illness in people either in the past or the current period are H3N2, H2N2, H1N1, and H1N2. H1N1 and H3N2 subtypes have caused

outbreaks in pigs and H7N7 and H3N8 viruses have caused outbreaks in horses. Therefore Influenza A viruses normally seen in one species sometimes can cross over and cause illness in another species. Until 1998, only H1N1 viruses circulated widely in the U.S. pig population. However, in 1998, H3N2 viruses from humans were introduced into the pig population and caused widespread disease among pigs [2].

Avian influenza viruses may be transmitted to humans in two main ways: Directly from birds or from avian virus-contaminated environments to people or through an intermediate host, such as a pig.

Influenza viruses have eight separate gene segments. The segmented genome allows viruses from different species to mix and create a new influenza A virus if viruses from two different species infect the same person or animal. For example, if a pig were infected with a human influenza virus and an avian influenza virus at the same time, the viruses could reassort and produce a new virus that had most of the genes from the human virus, but a hemagglutinin and/or neuraminidase from the avian virus (Antigenic shift). The resulting new virus might then be able to infect humans and spread from person to person, but it would have surface proteins (hemagglutinin and/or neuraminidase) not previously seen in influenza viruses that infect humans. . If this new virus causes illness in people and can be transmitted easily from person to person, an influenza pandemic can occur. It also is possible that the process of reassortment could occur in a human. A person could be infected with avian influenza and a human strain of

influenza at the same time. These viruses could reassort to create a new virus that had a hemagglutinin from the avian virus and other genes from the human virus.

Theoretically, influenza A viruses with a hemagglutinin against which humans have little or no immunity that have reassorted with a human influenza virus are more likely to result in sustained human-to-human transmission and pandemic influenza. [3, 4].

Bird flu is an infection caused by avian (bird) influenza (flu) viruses. These flu viruses occur naturally among birds. Wild birds worldwide carry the viruses in their intestines, but usually do not get sick from them. Bird flu is very contagious among birds and can make some domesticated birds, including chickens, ducks, and turkeys very sick and kill them. Several instances of human infections and outbreaks of avian influenza have been reported since 1997. Most cases of avian influenza infection in humans are thought to have resulted from contact with infected poultry or contaminated surfaces.

Confirmed instances of avian influenza viruses infecting humans since 1997 include:

***Influenza A (H5N1) virus** – also called “H5N1 virus” is influenza A virus subtype that occurs mainly in birds. It was first isolated from birds (terns) in South Africa in 1961. Like all bird flu viruses, H5N1 virus circulates among birds worldwide, is very contagious among birds, and can be deadly.

During the last decade highly pathogenic strains of avian influenza virus, including the H5N1 subtype, crossed the species barriers from birds to

humans and caused fatal disease. The Z strain of H5N1 subtype is characterized by pathogenicity to a larger number of animal species and by resistance to the older class of antiviral drugs. At present, two out of three general conditions for the onset of a pandemic have been met; namely, the emergence of a new virus and its ability to replicate in humans causing serious illness.

Outbreaks of influenza H5N1 occurred among poultry in eight countries in Asia (Cambodia, China, Indonesia, Japan, Laos, South Korea, Thailand, and Vietnam) during late 2003 and early 2004. At that time, more than 100 million birds in the affected countries either died from the disease or were killed in order to try to control the outbreak. By March 2004, the outbreak was reported to be under control. Beginning in late June 2004, however, new deadly outbreaks of influenza H5N1 among poultry were reported by several countries in Asia (Cambodia, China, Indonesia, Malaysia [first-time reports], Thailand, and Vietnam). It is believed that these outbreaks are ongoing [5, 6].

Avian influenza A (H5N1) infections occurred in both poultry and humans for the first time in Hong Kong, 1997. During this outbreak, 18 people were hospitalized and six of them died. To control the outbreak, authorities killed about 1.5 million chickens to remove the source of the virus. Scientists determined that the virus spread primarily from birds to humans, though rare person-to-person infection was noted

In 2003 Two cases of avian influenza A (H5N1) infection occurred among members of a Hong Kong family that had traveled to China. One person recovered, the other died. How or where these two family members were infected

was not determined. Another family member died of a respiratory illness in China, but no testing was done. From December 30, 2003, to March 17, 2004, 12 confirmed human cases of avian influenza A (H5N1) were reported in Thailand and 23 in Vietnam, resulting in a total of 23 deaths. Again, beginning in late June 2004, new lethal outbreaks of H5N1 among poultry were reported by several countries in Asia. The new outbreaks of H5N1 in poultry in Asia were followed by renewed sporadic reporting of human cases of H5N1 infection in Vietnam and Thailand beginning in August and continuing into 2005. In one isolated instance, probable limited human-to-human transmission occurred in Thailand in September [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13].

***Avian influenza A H9N2** illness was confirmed in two children in China and Hong Kong, 1999. Both patients recovered, and no additional cases were confirmed. Poultry was the source of infection. However, the possibility of person-to-person transmission could not be ruled out. Several additional human H9N2 infections were reported from mainland China in 1998-99.

***H7N2**, Virginia, 2002: Following an outbreak of H7N2 among poultry in the Shenandoah Valley poultry production area, one person was found to have serologic evidence of infection with H7N2.

***H7N7**, Netherlands, 2003: The Netherlands reported outbreaks of influenza A (H7N7) in poultry on several farms. Later, infections were reported among pigs and humans. In total, 89 people were confirmed to have H7N7 influenza virus infection

associated with this poultry outbreak. These cases occurred mostly among poultry workers. H7N7-associated illness included 78 cases of conjunctivitis (eye infections) only; 5 cases of conjunctivitis and influenza-like illnesses with cough, fever, and muscle aches; 2 cases of influenza-like illness only; and 4 cases that were classified as "other." There was one death among the 89 total cases. The death occurred in a veterinarian who visited one of the affected farms and developed acute respiratory distress syndrome and complications related to H7N7 infection. The majority of these cases occurred as a result of direct contact with infected poultry; however, Dutch authorities reported three possible instances of transmission from poultry workers to family members. Since that time, no other instances of H7N7 infection among humans have been reported [14, 15].

***H9N2**, Hong Kong, 2003: H9N2 infection was confirmed in a child in Hong Kong. The child was hospitalized but recovered.

***H7N2**, New York: In November 2003, a patient with serious underlying medical conditions was admitted to a hospital in New York with respiratory symptoms. One of the initial laboratory tests identified influenza A virus that was thought to be H1N1. The patient recovered and went home after a few weeks. Subsequent confirmatory tests conducted in March 2004 showed that the patient had been infected with an H7N2 avian influenza virus. An investigation to determine the source of infection is ongoing.

***H7N3** in Canada, 2004: In February 2004, human infections of H7N3 among poultry workers were associated with an H7N3 outbreak among poultry. The H7N3-associated illnesses consisted of eye infections. Surveillance identified two persons with confirmed avian influenza infection. Symptoms included conjunctivitis and mild influenza like illness [16]

Symptoms of Avian Influenza in Humans

The reported symptoms of avian influenza in humans have ranged from typical influenza-like symptoms (e.g., fever, cough, sore throat, and muscle aches) to eye infections (conjunctivitis), pneumonia, acute respiratory distress, viral pneumonia, and other severe and life-threatening complications. These symptoms are associated with lymphopenia. Avian influenza has been reported in a patient with fever and diarrhea but no respiratory symptoms. Avian influenza should be included in the differential diagnosis for patients with predominantly gastrointestinal symptoms, particularly if they have a history of exposure to poultry [17, 18].

Infection of children: Influenza viruses from chickens (H5N1) have caused outbreaks in children from both Vietnam and Thailand in 2004. All infected patients presented with fever and cough. Striking laboratory findings included leukopenia and thrombocytopenia. All children who developed progressive pneumonia with acute respiratory distress syndrome died. However, very few children received antiviral therapy [19, 20].

The diagnosis of influenza A (H5N1)

In many of the reported patients the diagnosis of influenza A (H5N1) was confirmed by means of viral culture or reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction with primers specific for H5 and N1[18,21]

Antiviral Agents for Influenza

Four different influenza antiviral drugs (amantadine, rimantadine, oseltamivir, and zanamivir) are approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the treatment and/or prophylaxis of influenza. All four have activity against influenza A viruses. However, sometimes influenza strains can become resistant to these drugs, and therefore the drugs may not always be effective. For example, analyses of some of the 2004 H5N1 viruses isolated from poultry and humans in Asia have shown that the viruses are resistant to two of the medications (amantadine and rimantadine). Monitoring of avian viruses for resistance to influenza antiviral medications is ongoing.

The efficacy of the neuraminidase inhibitor GS4104 (oseltamivir phosphate) against these H5N1 and H9N2 viruses has been demonstrated in mice. GS4071 (the active metabolite of oseltamivir) inhibited viral replication in MDCK cells (EC₅₀ values, 7.5-12 microM) and neuraminidase activity (IC₅₀ values, 7.0-15 nM).

When orally administered at doses of 1 and 10 mg/kg per day, GS4104 prevented death of mice infected with A/Hong Kong/156/97 (H5N1), mouse-

adapted A/Quail/Hong Kong/G1/97 (H9N2), or human A/Hong Kong/1074/99 (H9N2) viruses and

reduced virus titers in the lungs and prevented the spread of virus to the brain of mice infected with A/Hong Kong/156/97 (H5N1) and mouse-adapted A/Quail/Hong Kong/G1/97 (H9N2) viruses. When therapy was delayed until 36 h after exposure to the H5N1 virus, GS4104 was still effective and significantly increased the number of survivors as compared with control. Oral administration of GS4104 (0.1 mg/kg per day) in combination with rimantadine (1 mg/kg per day) reduced the number of deaths of mice infected with 100 MLD (50) of H9N2 virus and prevented the deaths of mice infected with 5 MLD (50) of virus [22].

The orally administered neuraminidase (NA) inhibitor RWJ-270201, zanamivir, and oseltamivir have been shown in mice to inhibit avian influenza viruses NA activity and replication in tissue culture and have protective effect against lethal H5N1 and H9N2 virus infection. In vitro, NA inhibition by RWJ-270201 (50% inhibitory concentration, 0.9 to 4.3 nM) was superior to that by zanamivir and oseltamivir carboxylate. RWJ-270201 inhibited the replication of avian influenza viruses of both Eurasian and American lineages in MDCK cells (50% effective concentration, 0.5 to 11.8 microM). Mice given 10 mg of RWJ-270201 per kg of body weight per day were completely protected against lethal challenge with influenza A/Hong Kong/156/97 (H5N1) and A/quail/Hong Kong/G1/97 (H9N2) viruses. Both RWJ-270201 and oseltamivir significantly reduced virus titers in mouse lungs at daily dosages of 1.0 and 10 mg/kg and prevented the spread of virus to the brain. When treatment began 48 h after exposure to H5N1 virus, 10 mg of RWJ-270201/kg/day protected 50% of mice

from death. RWJ-270201, zanamivir or oseltamivir can be of potential clinical use for treatment of emerging influenza viruses that may be transmitted from birds to humans [23].

The risk to humans from bird flu

The risk from bird flu is generally low to most people because the viruses occur mainly among birds and do not usually infect humans. However, during an outbreak of bird flu among poultry (domesticated chicken, ducks, turkeys), there is a possible risk to people who have contact with infected birds or surfaces that have been contaminated with excretions from infected birds. The current outbreak of avian influenza A (H5N1) among poultry in Asia (see below) is an example of a bird flu outbreak that has caused human infections and deaths. In such situations, people should avoid contact with infected birds or contaminated surfaces, and should be careful when handling and cooking poultry.

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